

REPORT ON THE TRAINING ACTIVITIES – YEAR 1

Report on the training activities	
Date:	[30/09/2025]
Version:	[v1.0]

PROJECT	
Project number:	[101152452]
Project acronym:	[U-SPY]
Project name:	[Artificial metalloenzymes Using SPY protein]
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Planned trainings in the application:

Training	Task number	Expected time	Comment/Modification	Implementation time
Training for the use of instrumentation	T4.2	M1-11	Hand-on trainings by the group members. Courses by operators (out of group) for fluorimetry and NMR spectrometer.	M1-12
Training for the use of software and calculation tools	T4.3	M1-6	Online EMBL-EBI training on AlphaFold 2 and 3. Hands on training on Pymol, and HypSpec.	M4-M8
Training on UNIPR digital resources	T4.4	M1-6	Reaxys, SciFinder, IRIS	M1-M4
Safety training	T4.4	M1	Online courses in English	M6
Trainings by UNIPR Research Support Unit on data management and project management	T4.5	M1-3	Online training	M1
Italian language course	T4.8	M1-24	Online course by UNIPR. Probably further courses in the next semester.	M1-M7
Online courses and workshops on sustainability,	T4.9	M1-24	Participation in EUGREEN workshop.	M1, M2, M4, M7

IPR, research integrity and ethics organized by European Commission, RUS and EU GREEN Alliance			Online presentations: “Circular Dichroism (CD) Spectroscopy applied to Peptides” (by Italian Peptide Society); “Copper-catalysed carbon-heteroatom bond-forming processes” (by ChemistryWorld); “Selective, Catalytic Functionalization and Deconstruction Reactions” (by ACS Science Talks).	Plans for participating in further workshops online.
Online training by Coursera courses	T4.10	M1-24		Planned in M13-24
In person courses “Inorganic Systems in Biology” and “Visible-light Promoted Reactions”	T4.11	M6-12	As these are in Italian, English alternatives will be searched.	M13-24
Additional:				
Online training for exploitation: participation in the 5th ERC Starting Grant mentoring event of the Young Academy of Europe and Academia Europaea Budapest Knowledge Hub.				M12

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	30.09.2025	Initial version

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